

THE MOUNTAIN PRODUCT – SANOGENIC VECTOR

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Abstract

Based on the Hippocratic exhortation of 2,400 years ago: "let food be your medicine and medicine (cure) be your food", this scientific approach aims to argue the use of mountain products as an alternative to a medical regimen aimed at preventing, relieving or treating certain diseases. Research in recent decades has shown that diet is one of the key determinants of health, with an unhealthy diet being the perfect support for modern diseases such as cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, lung disease, obesity, cancer, etc. Analysing the incidence of disease in an industrialising and urbanising society (which leads to changes in eating habits through the consumption of high calorie and fat-dense foods, low dietary fibre and low-quality protein), we can see the importance of food as a medicine. Mountain products are foods with a high nutritional value, unpolluted, tasty, healthy and come from plants living in a clean and quiet environment and from animals consuming the highest quality forage from mountain pastures with high nutritional value. Basically, through its natural characteristics, but also the stored energy value, the mountain product transforms the most precious natural elements – pure water, clean air, soil unaffected by chemicals, into high quality products that can influence the health of the human body. Out of responsibility for our health, we need to choose those components that meet the requirement of being compatible with the biochemical structure of the human body and are in full accordance with the energy of living.

Keywords: mountain product, health, healthy eating, bioactive compounds, natural therapy.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, attitudes towards health have received a great deal of attention, largely due to the fact that health is seen as a resource that enables other vital benefits (Paraschiv, 2003). Even if in the past healthy eating represented a process that was part of the nature of things, today, in an increasingly chemicalized and processed era, the return to a food-medicine represents a paradigm shift, but also an act of assumption from consumers.

Research in recent decades (Grădinaru, 2012 and 2022; Lad et al, 2017; Para, 2015; Paraschiv, 2003; Park, 2017; World Health Organization, 2022) has shown that diet is one of the most important determinants of health, with an unhealthy diet being the perfect support for many modern diseases: cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, lung disease, obesity, cancer, etc. This is the main reason why people should pay much more attention to dietary behaviour. Today, due to abundance – which often leads to the overshadowing of the origin of products and traceability (Grădinaru, 2022), availability, but also the fast pace, food behaviour involves choices: the choice of food, the choice of quantity, but also the choice of the time of consumption, because food is not only food but also a complex biological-psychological whole influenced by accessibility, financial constraints, religious and cultural customs (Cazacu, 2018). Irrational eating behaviour no longer takes into account the cultural location of the product (Grădinaru, 2022), and this leads to inappropriate choices,

which ends in the consumption of food of poor nutritional quality, which not only does not bring benefits, but also causes major metabolic imbalances.

Analysing the incidence of diseases in a society undergoing a process of industrialisation and urbanisation, which entails changes in eating habits through the consumption of high calorie-fat density foods, low dietary fibre content and low-quality proteins (Graur, 2006), we can see the importance given to food as medicine. Through their content of vitamins, minerals and amino acids, medicine-foods can influence the health of the human body.

Eating should not be seen strictly as an act that covers a physiological need, it represents a much more complex action involving choices, tastes, behaviours that give the phenomenon its qualitative note (Brillat-Savarin, 2019). With the progress of mankind, the nature and type of food have undergone considerable changes, modern man's diet is no longer made up of natural products that required a relatively short preparation time but of products that have undergone a high degree of processing, this being the perfect support for the unfavourable trends that characterise contemporary food. Today, new neuromarketing techniques (using sensory marketing tools in particular) are deliberately inducing an uncontrolled stimulation of appetite and eating as a social act, not as a natural response to a basic need. This is why the food being promoted is processed and packaged as attractively as possible to attract the customer and make it available for immediate and long-term consumption. Unfortunately, there are still few people who question the issue of the tribute of abundance and how dangerous food can be through excessive chemicalisation betrayed by a long shelf life.

For this reason, it is necessary to return to simple food and the use of food therapy, because the medicine-food is prepared, used and adapted to each individual consumer/patient depending on the symptoms, the stage of the disease and the psycho-mental profile of the patient (Paraschiv, 2003). Medicine-food is the viable solution for sustaining life energy, replacing a degraded food – which lacks enzymes and has the effect of causing major metabolic and energy imbalances.

By choosing a bio-stimulating medicine-food (of plant or animal origin) that is compatible with the human body, the risk of complications attributed to the side effects of most synthetic drugs is eliminated. The health and state of harmony of each individual is closely related to the food they eat (Bieler, 1994). When opting for the use of medicine-foods it is imperative to take into account the quantity in which they are consumed, the time of day, and the way in which they are consumed (in most cases it is recommended to use products of plant or animal origin in their raw state). Last but not least, it should be emphasised that the use of medicine-foods is conditioned by the natural environment, climatic conditions, the patient's psychological profile and spiritual values.

The present research proposal is based on the Hippocratic exhortation of 2,400 years ago: “let food be your medicine and medicine (cure) be your food”, because the earliest concerns about daily nutrition as a therapeutic vector for the treatment of diseases belong to Hippocrates. This paper aims to argue for the use of mountain products as an alternative to a medicinal regime aimed at preventing, alleviating or treating certain diseases. Starting from the main objective of sustainable exploitation and exploitation of mountain resources, the paper aims to argue the use of mountain products as an alternative to a medicinal regime, which also aims to prevent, improve or treat certain diseases.

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHOD

According to the methodological approach, the present research is based on an interdisciplinary analysis, providing information on the therapeutic properties of mountain products. A total of 67 scientific papers, reports and specialist papers were analysed, consulting the Google Scholar platform and selecting the results in order of relevance according to the key phrase "food-medicine". The conclusions of this study resulted from research which involved a review of the relevant literature on mountain products and their therapeutic qualities. Furthermore, we performed a mirror comparison for two food products (goat milk and whey) that can be used as medicine-foods, for which the chemical profile (protein, casein, cholesterol, fat, terpene, minerals, fatty acids) according to the literature was highlighted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Caring for your personal health resource by drawing on the gifts of nature should be a priority at any age, counterbalancing the toxic behaviour of waiting for compensated drugs. Food is one of the environmental factors with a major impact on the human body, as food is either a vector that supports health through balanced and rational consumption, or, on the contrary, can play a decisive role in the deterioration of health through chaotic and often excessive consumption. Eating behaviour should not be generated only by instinct but should be the result of education and self-education (Blîndul, 2021). In case of illness it is very important to change the diet, choosing the one that supports the state of health, firstly in order not to consume foods that are unfavourable to the imbalance created in the body, and the second reason is the choice of medicine-foods that support the body in fighting the disease.

Unfortunately, today, food labelling is closer to the chemical industry than to the food industry (Hieke & Taylor, 2012). Consumer awareness that we are what we eat was the point at which responsible consumers attributed the right value to the simple but oh-so-tasty ingredients that were once found in every mountain household: milk, cream, eggs, butter, meat, wild mushrooms, berries, spices, herbs, etc. We find all these products today under the generic name of mountain product (Gorlier et al., 2012; Bentivoglio et al., 2019, Rey, 2021). The harsh conditions characteristic of the mountain area determined by the physical-geographical peculiarities, altitude, slope and vegetation period have not been conducive to the development of intensive (chemical-using) agriculture but only to the development of extensive (nature-friendly) agriculture (Rey, 2008).

Due to its natural characteristics and stored energy value, mountain food products transform all the valuable natural elements (soil, pure water, clean air) into products with a high nutritional and health quality level.

The works dealing with the food and therapeutic sectors in the well-known collection "Corpus Hippocraticum" – a collection of about 60 ancient Greek medical works (On Food; Diet in Acute Diseases; On Air, Water and Places; Food or Nourishment) show that the basis of Hippocratic medication and the diet recommended to patients is natural extracts from plant and animal products (Paraschiv 2003).

Metabolism affected by diet is one of the main physiological phenomena influencing health. Whereas in the past, generally due to poor sanitary conditions, infectious diseases predominated in mass pathology, metabolic diseases have recently taken a leading place in

mass pathology. For this reason too, there is a need to exploit the health-giving potential of food. If nutrition acts as a physiological factor, then food nutrients can also have a therapeutic effect, especially when they affect the energy level of human physiology. Indeed, in essence, the dietary factor, like the pharmacological factor, aims to solve the same problem – restoring the body's physiology to normal. The difference is that the pharmacological approach solves the problem from one end (from the symptoms of its manifestation), and the nutritional approach from the other, from the beginning. For food to manifest its therapeutic effect, it must be treated as strictly as pharmacological drugs – knowing the norm and following the recommendations and not living by the principle of freedom and infinity (Mereuță & Strutinschi, 2019, p. 51).

The curative value of food products can determine their hierarchy. In the interwar period, due to its nutritional qualities, milk was the most appreciated food, followed by beehive products, eggs, fruits and vegetables (Baciu, 2014). Food therapy exists through the convictions and efforts of some doctors, who realized its possibilities in the light of current knowledge about pharmacological mechanisms and biochemical processes of the component substances. Hippocrates' call to treat illness through adequate food, fresh air and rest is synthesised in the healing power of nature acting from within (Paraschiv, 2003).

In this paper we set out to study two mountain foods: specifically a product (goat milk) and a by-product (whey from cow's milk) in order to demonstrate (based on the scientific literature) their curative value. In the first stage, the chemical composition of mountain goat's milk/cheese was compared with goat's milk/cheese from lowland/rural animals. It can be seen that mountain goat milk contains a higher amount of protein, casein, fat, zinc, terpene, mono and polyunsaturated fatty acids, and conjugated linoleic acid compared to milk from lowland/rural areas (Table 1). The study by Peña-Avelino (2023) showed a lower atherogenic and thrombogenic index in mountain milk compared to lowland milk. Also, Na, Mg and cholesterol contents were lower in mountain milk compared to lowland milk.

Table 1. Chemical composition of mountain goat milk versus lowland goat milk

Category	Component	Plain/Lowland	Mountain	References
Composition	Dry substance %	11.40	12.29	Barlowska et al., 2018
	Protein %	2.95	3.12	
	Casein %	2.37	2.51	
	Fat %	3.29	3.91	
	Cholesterol (mg/100 mL)	16.21	15.53	
Minerals	Ca (mg/L)	1182.0	1022.0	Kedzierska-Matysek et al. 2015
	Na (mg/L)	366.9	285.4	
	Mg (mg/L)	132.6	109.1	
	Zn (mg/L)	2.56	3.50	
Terpene	α -Pinene (ng/g)	65.5	281	Borge et al. 2016
	α -Thujene (ng/g)	0.0	17.9	
	Total terpene (ng/g)	169	444	
Fatty acids	Saturated fatty acids (g/100g)	76.78	76.23	

Category	Component	Plain/Lowland	Mountain	References
	Monosaturated fatty acids (g/100g)	21.85	22.06	Peña-Avelino, 2023
	Polyunsaturated fatty acids (g/100g)	1.36	1.70	
	Conjugated linoleic acid (g/100g)	1.08	1.41	
Health	Atherogenic index	4.24	3.36	
	Thrombogenic index	2.34	2.00	

Regarding the chemical composition of cow whey, a higher content of lactose, fat and K was observed in whey from the mountain area compared to that from the lowland/rural area (Table 2). No significant differences were observed between the two by-products from different areas in terms of α -lactalbumin, ash, P, Na and Mg content (Johansen et al. 2002).

Table 2. Chemical composition of cow whey in mountain versus lowland areas

Category	Component	Plain/Lowland	Mountain	References
Nutritional composition	Lactose (g/L)	48.42	66.56	Johansen et al. 2002
	B-lactoglobulin (g/L)	3.15	3.10	
	α -lactalbumin (g/L)	1.03	1.03	
	Ash	5.18	5.19	
	Fat	1.82	2.67	
Minerals	K	1.53	1.63	
	P	0.45	0.47	
	Ca	0.40	0.43	
	Na	0.38	0.39	
	Mg	0.08	0.09	

Due to their biochemical structure and nutritional value, mountain foods ensure or restore, where appropriate, optimal balance in the body, contribute to the physical and mental development of patients by providing the body with the necessary resources, support immunity and enhance quality of life.

This paper supports the curative-therapeutic potential of mountain foods resulting from the correct, well-calculated, balanced and wise choice of mountain foods according to the ailment. It is imperative to take into account the way in which the food is prepared (which ones require heat treatment and which do not), compliance with hygiene and health conditions, and the consumption time of the food in question.

Therapeutic properties of goat's milk:

- two glasses of goat's milk cover one's daily calcium needs, 20% of one's vitamin B intake and a significant amount of potassium and phosphorus (Park & Haenlein, 2007; Krstanovic et al., 2010; Saikia, 2022);
- very good immunostimulant (Cook et al., 1993; Alkaisy et al., 2023);

- rich in oligosaccharides (similar to those in breast milk); benefits of goat's milk include protection of intestinal flora against pathogens (LaraVilloslada et al., 2004; Lad, 2017; Raynal-Ljutovac et al., 2008; Sousa et al., 2019);
- anticarcinogenic action (Belury, 1995; Jirillo et al., 2010; Parodi, 1994; Verruck et al., 2019);
- reduces body fat (Pariza et al., 1996);
- rich in vitamin A, it takes care of healthy nails and skin (Park, 2017);
- goat milk has antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal properties (Park and Haenleinet, 2007; Niaz et al., 2019);
- keeps cholesterol under control because goat's milk is rich in fatty acids beneficial to the body (Haenlein, 1992; Lad, 2017; Lopez-Aliaga et al., 2005).
- has antioxidant effect (Geissler & Powers, 2010);
- anti-inflammatory properties (Lad, 2017; Sousa et al., 2019);
- beneficial for heart health due to its high potassium levels; potassium is a vasodilator that relaxes blood vessels. Regular consumption of goat's milk can prevent atherosclerosis, stroke, heart attack and other coronary complications. (Posati and Orr, 1976; Haenlein, 2004).

Therapeutic properties of whey (from cow's milk):

The Italians have a proverb that has been around since the 16th century: If everyone were fed whey, doctors would go bankrupt.

- burns fat – whey protein stimulates the body to produce cholecystokinin, a peptide hormone of the gastrointestinal system responsible for stimulating the digestion of fats and proteins and which also provides a feeling of satiety (Bulut & Akin, 2009; Khamrui & Rajorhia, 1998; Zemel, 2004);
- ideal source of energy and nutrients for athletes due to the high amount of protein with high biological value (Kimball, 2002; Layman, 2003; Macwan et al., 2016);
- whey proteins help most in skeletal muscle growth (Jelen, 2002; Paddon et al., 2005; Patel, 2012;);
- antiviral, antibacterial properties (Floris, 2003; Pan et al., 2006; Sprong, 2001);
- stops the growth of cancerous tumours (Bounous et al, 2000; Hakkak, 2001; Harper, 2004; Macwan et al., 2016);
- suppresses the intestinal colonisation of *Helicobacter pylori* (Collins et al., 2006);
- helps lower blood pressure and cholesterol (Kawase, 2000);
- strengthens immunity (Harper, 2004; Macwan et al., 2016; Mercier, 2004);
- combats anaemia, helps iron assimilation (Macwan et al., 2016);
- prevents osteoporosis (Macwan et al., 2016; Onwulata & Huth, 2008; Takada, 1996);
- prevents premature ageing through whey's antioxidant qualities (ability to protect the skin against free radicals, which intensify the ageing process) (Bounous et al., 1989; Macwan et al., 2016; De Wit, 1998);
- treats eczema: in compress applications (Bucci & Unlu, 2000);
- combats insomnia, increases the body's resistance to effort and stress: whey is rich in the amino acid L-tryptophan, which can help improve cognitive function in stressed people (Macwan et al., 2016; Markus et al., 2005).

CONCLUSION

Physical and mental balance is achieved through a proper diet based on quality, unpolluted products. A decisive role in this is played by the ability of patients to transform what they take in physically, mentally and spiritually into energy. Today's sad reality is that artificial food has multiplied, while live food has diminished considerably. Moreover, people's attention is distracted, and in the act of feeding they put pleasure and craving first, not the motivation of the need for health. For this reason, it is necessary to understand, as consumers, that food is not only intended to satisfy the primary need (hunger) but also to prevent and treat illnesses, given that the more than 200,000 synthetic medicines (with a chemical structure unknown to the human body) on the market are associated with a series of side effects.

The chemical composition of dairy products in the mountain area compared to those in the lowlands supports their superior quality. Thus, a higher content of terpenes and health-promoting fatty acids such as polyunsaturated fatty acids and conjugated linoleic acid was observed. There is a need for studies on the differentiation of mountain products on the market and for consumer information on the results of such research.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization, A.M.; Data curation, A.A. and A.I.S.; Formal analysis, A.M.; Investigation, A.M., B.D.C. and A.I.S.; Methodology, A.M.; Visualization, C.C.B; Roles/Writing – original draft, A.M., C.C.B.; Writing – review & editing, A.M., A.I.S.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD STATEMENT

Not applicable.

INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

Not applicable.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data supporting the results of this study are available within the article [and/or] its supplementary materials.

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